

ОЦІНКА ЯКОСТІ ЗАЙНЯТОСТІ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ЯК ІНСТРУМЕНТ УПРАВЛІННЯ

Гурбанова І. М.

ASSESSMENT OF EMPLOYEE QUALITY AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL

Gurbanova I. M.

In the modern era, the role of human capital in the efficient functioning of enterprises is steadily increasing. Although traditional management approaches mainly focus on employee productivity, the volume of work performed, and outcomes, these approaches do not fully cover the level of satisfaction of the employee as an individual with their work and the qualitative aspects of employment. However, employees' satisfaction, motivation, and opportunities to realize their potential directly affect their labor productivity and, in general, the efficiency of the enterprise's performance [3].

From this perspective, evaluating the level of employment not only quantitatively but also qualitatively is of particular importance. The aim of the article is to clarify the use of information obtained from the individual assessment of the quality of employment of employees in the effective management of the enterprise.

At the macro level, the level of employment is calculated, but the percentage of those employed in efficient (quality) employment is not determined. In our opinion, in the modern era there is a need to qualitatively assess employment at the individual, micro, and macro levels. The higher this indicator, the higher the provision of decent jobs, which corresponds to Goal 8 of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the UN [4].

Traditionally, the assessment of employment is carried out based on quantitative indicators (the number of economically active population and the number of employed within them). However, these indicators do not reflect the personal position of the employee, that is, how satisfied they are with their job, to what extent they are able to realize their skills and labor potential in their position and under the conditions created, and thus how satisfied they are with their work.

Various methods for evaluating employees are recommended in the literature on human resource management [1; 2, p. 184]. Most of these methods reflect the position of the enterprise, while the position of the individual remains secondary.

In modern management approaches, employee satisfaction and well-being are considered as a strategic resource of the organization. According to such approaches, the employee's attitude toward their work is not only an individual matter but also an important factor influencing overall internal organizational outcomes. Therefore, measuring the quality of employment allows for more effective decision-making and implementation in management.

We believe that each individual knows their own potential better, and everyone can determine to what extent their salary satisfies their material and moral needs. Even individuals with the same qualifications, working in the same position with the same salary, will have different levels of satisfaction. The extent to which wages satisfy them also depends on family income, owned property, and other factors. Moral satisfaction, in turn, depends on their ability to realize their potential at work. Thus, each person can evaluate their own employment satisfaction, while external third-party evaluations will be relative.

Therefore, assessing the quality of employment of personnel from their own perspective can be beneficial both for themselves and for the enterprise. Subsequently, it will also be possible to measure the level of employment at the macro level.

At the micro level, that is, at the enterprise level, this is easier to implement. Through an online survey, it is possible to learn the opinions of all employees about their work. First, individual-level assessments are obtained, and based on these, the quality of employment at the enterprise level is evaluated.

The article proposes calculating a general index based on the individual assessment of employees' employment quality. For this purpose, the following main criteria can be selected:

- adequacy of income;
- correspondence of the position to education level and specialization;

- compatibility with skills;
- opportunity to realize labor potential;
- moral satisfaction from the job;
- training and career advancement opportunities.
- stress level (unlike other indicators, a lower value is considered preferable);

Each employee evaluates their job on a scale from 0 to 100 for the specified criteria. Then, by calculating the individual's employment quality, the arithmetic mean is obtained. If we consider employees with a score above 70 as having quality (efficient) employment, by dividing their number by the total number of employees, we can determine the level of efficient employment in the enterprise. Its benefit for the enterprise is that the data obtained from surveys conducted among employees serve as an important source of information for management. Through these indicators:

- individual problems and expectations of employees are identified;
- areas with low satisfaction are determined;
- motivation, incentive, and wage policies are improved;
- more optimal use of human resources potential is ensured.

As a result, both the problems of employees are revealed and their needs are more fully met, and the overall productivity of the enterprise increases. The only drawback here may be related to respondents not providing sincere and accurate answers.

References

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